

FORMATION OF COMPOSITIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE VISUAL ARTS
TEACHERS THROUGH INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of developing compositional competence in future visual arts teachers through interactive teaching methods. The essence and content of compositional competence, its structural components, and its role in painting classes are substantiated from a scientific and pedagogical perspective. Furthermore, the didactic potential of interactive methods such as brainstorming, small group work, problem-based learning, reflection, and project-based learning in developing compositional thinking is highlighted. The research findings indicate that the use of interactive methods contributes to the development of independent thinking, creative approach, aesthetic taste, and analytical skills among students. The article also proposes mechanisms for the step-by-step development of compositional competence and provides methodological recommendations.

Keywords: compositional competence, compositional thinking, interactive methods, painting, visual arts education, creative activity, aesthetic education, problem-based learning, reflection, pedagogical technologies.

The issue of developing the compositional competence of future visual arts teachers through interactive methods is considered one of the priority directions of the modern pedagogical process. In today's conditions of globalization, the education system is required not only to provide knowledge, but also to form individuals who think creatively, can make independent decisions, and possess well-developed aesthetic thinking. In particular, the field of visual arts education, by its artistic and aesthetic nature, requires the development of not only practical skills in students, but also complex compositional thinking. In this regard, it is of great importance to scientifically study the possibilities of interactive methods in shaping the compositional competence of future visual arts teachers.

The concept of compositional competence is multifaceted; it implies a student's ability to organize a visual image logically and aesthetically, to ensure harmony between form and content, to manage spatial arrangement, to harmonize color and light-shadow relationships, and to express an ideological concept through artistic means. This competence relies not only on theoretical knowledge, but also on practical experience, visual observation, artistic thinking, and creative independence. For a future teacher, compositional competence manifests itself in two directions: first, the ability to independently solve compositional tasks in personal creative activity; second, the ability to methodologically and correctly convey the principles of composition to students. In traditional teaching practice, composition is often taught through demonstrating ready-made examples, analyzing them, and copying. Although such an approach develops certain technical skills, it does not sufficiently foster students' independent compositional thinking. As a result, they tend to rely on ready-made schemes, experience difficulties in generating new ideas, and demonstrate passivity in independently solving compositional problems. Therefore, in modern pedagogy, teaching models based on interactive methods are increasingly being applied.

Interactive methods are a set of pedagogical technologies that ensure active student participation in the learning process and stimulate thinking, analysis, evaluation, and discussion. Their main characteristic is that students do not receive knowledge in a ready-made form; instead, they acquire it through independent inquiry, collaboration, communication, and creative activity. This process plays a crucial role in the formation of compositional thinking, since composition always involves choice, comparison, consideration of alternatives, and finding the most optimal solution. In developing the compositional competence of future visual arts teachers, it is essential first to ensure deep mastery of the principles of composition—such as balance, rhythm, contrast, proportion, focal point, unity, dynamics, and statics. However, these concepts yield effective results not merely through theoretical definitions, but when studied through interactive activities integrated with practical exercises. For example, through the “brainstorming” method, students may be assigned to propose various compositional solutions based on a given theme. In this process, they complement each other’s ideas, generate new concepts, and gain the opportunity to move beyond stereotypical thinking. The small group work method holds particular significance in shaping compositional competence. During group activities, students discuss a compositional problem collectively, divide roles, distribute tasks, and develop a final artistic solution. For instance, they may be given tasks such as “Create a dynamic composition within a single color range” or “Create the illusion of movement using static objects.” Such assignments encourage students to explore, experiment, and deeply understand compositional tools. In solving the problem, they test their knowledge and skills and seek new approaches.

Methods of visual analysis and reflection also play an important role in strengthening compositional competence. Students discuss their own works and those of their peers, identify strengths and weaknesses, and analyze compositional errors. This process fosters critical thinking and teaches the conscious application of aesthetic criteria. Most importantly, students learn to evaluate their own creative activity, which ensures methodological reflection in their future teaching practice. Painting classes organized on the basis of interactive methods broaden students’ imagination. In creating a composition, they not only arrange objects but also shape a meaningful concept. The harmony between idea and form is the most important indicator of compositional competence. If a student can consciously determine the compositional center, correctly distribute secondary elements, and purposefully use color contrast, it indicates that their compositional thinking has been formed.

For a future visual arts teacher, compositional competence is closely connected with methodological competence. They must not only be able to construct a composition themselves, but also develop artistic thinking in their students. Interactive methods are significant in this regard in two ways: on the one hand, they develop the student’s personal creative potential; on the other hand, they form pedagogical experience that can be applied in future teaching practice. For example, through the “gallery method,” where students display their works on the wall for collective discussion, the experience is reinforced in the student’s consciousness as an effective teaching method.

In conclusion, the development of compositional competence in future visual arts teachers through interactive methods is one of the important tasks of modern education. This process requires the integration of theoretical knowledge, practical exercises, and creative activity. Interactive methods increase students’ personal engagement, develop independent thinking, and teach them to consciously solve compositional problems. As a result, a specialist with developed aesthetic taste, formed

compositional thinking, and pedagogical mastery is prepared. Such a teacher plays a significant role in enhancing the artistic and aesthetic culture of future generations.

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